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Ideology, Power and Apostasy in Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero*

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Abstract

This study interrogated ideology, power, and apostasy in Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero* through the lens of Critical Discourse Analysis and pragmatics. The research was necessitated by the gap in scholarship, where earlier studies addressed satire, power relations, or pragmatic strategies separately without integrating them to examine how discourse constructs apostasy as a linguistic, ideological, and

socio-religious phenomenon. The specific objectives of the study were to investigate ideology, power, and the language of apostasy; explore apostasy, power, and gendered resistance; analyse the discourse of power, apostasy, and the mask of holiness; examine the language of violence, irony, and disillusionment; and evaluate apostasy, ideology, and the corruption of power. A qualitative design was employed, using purposive sampling of dialogues from the play, which were thematically analysed to reveal linguistic patterns and discourse markers. The study found that Jeroboam's discourse revealed how apostasy is enacted through manipulation of faith and ideology, the silencing of gendered voices, and the masking of materialistic ambitions in spiritual pretence. The study concluded that Soyinka uses satire, irony, and discourse strategies to expose the contradictions of false religiosity and the corruption of power in religious discourse. The study contributed to existing knowledge by linking apostasy directly to discourse strategies of power and ideology, offering both theoretical advancement in African literary and linguistic studies and practical relevance as a cautionary framework for interrogating religious and political rhetoric.

Keywords: Apostasy, Ideology, Power, Discourse, Soyinka

Introduction

The social and historical context of Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero* reflects postcolonial Nigeria, where religion and politics frequently intersect

with questions of morality, power, and social order. Soyinka situates the narrative within a society experiencing rapid cultural transformation, in which religious leaders often manipulate faith to advance personal and political interests. According to Davoodifar and Pourya (2015), Soyinka's drama provides a Foucauldian perspective on power relations, illustrating how authority is negotiated through discourse rather than mere institutional control. Ajiboye (2020) notes that Soyinka employs pragmatic strategies in his portrayal of Jero to expose how language serves as both a tool of deception and a weapon of domination. In a related dimension, Jegede (2024a) observes that language and power dynamics in Nigerian drama mirror wider societal hierarchies, where discourse sustains inequality and manipulates belief systems. The study of Soyinka's text has also been extended to rhetorical strategies, with Jegede, Yusuf, Aliyu, and Aladetan (2024) showing that impoliteness is deliberately deployed to foreground hypocrisy and false piety. Within the Yoruba worldview, language functions as a site of negotiation between respect, power, and social expectation, as Jegede and Arubuola (2025) explain in their analysis of politeness and impoliteness in traditional Ijala poetry. These perspectives converge to reveal the layered nature of Soyinka's satire, which critiques both the institutionalisation of religion and the socio-political structures that sustain its misuse. In this context, *The Trials of Brother Jero* emerges as a critical text that engages with questions of ideology, apostasy, and the corruption of authority in African societies.

Studies on Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero* have extensively examined the play as a satire of religious hypocrisy, political manipulation, and social decay. For instance, Mireku-Gyimah (2013) reveals Soyinka's satirical strategies in critiquing false religiosity, while Davoodifar and Pourya (2015) employ a Foucauldian lens to explore power dynamics in the text. Other scholars, such as Mackwan (2018) and Ajiboye (2020), have focused on satire, conflict, and pragmatic roles in the play. Similarly, Abisola (2011), Osoba (2014), and Ekpe, Anita and Ako (2013) discuss Soyinka's language engineering and its critical engagement with social issues. However, these studies, though valuable, tend to focus either on satire or on the socio-political implications of Soyinka's art, without offering an integrated analysis that connects ideology, power, and the language of apostasy; apostasy, power, and gendered resistance; the discourse of power, apostasy, and the mask of holiness; the language of violence, irony, and disillusionment; and apostasy, ideology, and the corruption of power. This gap is problematic because it overlooks how Soyinka's dramatization of apostasy is not only a critique of religion but also a discourse of power that exposes deeper ideological struggles within Nigerian society.

Addressing this gap, the present study offers a more subtle understanding of the intersection between discourse, ideology, and power in the play, thereby expanding scholarship beyond satire into the pragmatics of religious apostasy. This research is significant as it contributes to the development of literary and linguistic studies by foregrounding how language operates as a tool for constructing, masking, and resisting power in religious and socio-political contexts.

Discourse Analysis and Its Application in Literary Studies

Discourse analysis is a multidisciplinary approach that examines how language is used to construct meaning, convey ideology, and establish power relations within a given social context. It explores both linguistic structures and the broader socio-cultural influences that shape communication (Gee, 2018). Discourse, in this sense, is not merely a reflection of reality but an active force that constructs and maintains social hierarchies, identities, and belief systems (Wodak & Meyer, 2021). Scholars have applied discourse analysis to various fields, including media studies, political communication, and sociology, but its relevance to literary studies is particularly significant. Literature functions as a powerful medium for encoding social, political, and ideological discourses, often providing insight into dominant power structures and marginalized voices within society (Fairclough, 2015). Through literary discourse analysis, scholars can uncover how narratives shape public perception, reinforce dominant ideologies, or challenge existing power structures. The analysis of character interactions, dialogue, and narrative strategies enables a good understanding of how texts reflect and influence social realities. This approach is especially useful in postcolonial literature, where themes of power, oppression, and identity are central to the narrative framework (Simpson & Mayr, 2019).

Applying discourse analysis to literary studies allows scholars to investigate how authors use language to critique societal structures, expose ideological biases, or reinforce cultural norms. Texts such as Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero* serve as rich sources for discourse analysis because they engage with themes of religious authority, deception, and social manipulation through character dialogue and interactions. Soyinka's play satirizes the ways in which religious leaders exploit discourse to establish and sustain dominance over their followers, making it an ideal subject for critical discourse analysis (Gikandi, 2019). Through examining lexical choices, rhetorical strategies, and conversational structures, scholars can uncover the subtle mechanisms through which power and ideology operate in the text (Van Dijk, 2015). The study of discourse in literary texts does not only enhance literary interpretation but also

contributes to broader discussions on how language functions as a tool of control and resistance in society. As literature reflects and critiques real-world social structures, discourse analysis provides a valuable methodological framework for understanding the deeper ideological implications of texts and their relevance to contemporary socio-political realities (Wodak, 2020).

Studies on Ideology and Power in Religious Discourse

Religious discourse has long been recognised as a powerful tool for shaping ideology and maintaining authority within societies. Studies have shown that religious language is not only a means of spiritual communication but also a mechanism for reinforcing power structures and legitimising dominant ideologies (Fairclough, 2015). Religious leaders and institutions often use discourse to establish moral and social norms, positioning themselves as gatekeepers of divine truth and authority (Van Dijk, 2008). The strategic use of religious rhetoric, metaphors, and narratives enables the construction of ideological frameworks that shape collective beliefs and behaviours (Wodak, 2020). Research in discourse studies reveals how religious texts and sermons employ persuasive linguistic strategies to sustain hierarchical relationships, marginalise dissenting voices, and promote obedience among followers (Richardson, 2019; Jegede & Lawal, 2023). The role of intertextuality in religious discourse is also significant, as religious leaders draw upon sacred texts, historical references, and doctrinal interpretations to reinforce their ideological positions (Chilton, 2022). This interplay between language, ideology, and power is particularly evident in societies where religion is deeply intertwined with politics, governance, and social order. Studies on religious discourse in Africa, for instance, reveal how preachers manipulate language to control congregations, justify socio-political structures, and resist external influences perceived as threats to religious orthodoxy (Asad, 2018; Jegede & Okere, 2025).

Power in religious discourse is often maintained through ritualised speech, authoritative tone, and the strategic framing of theological concepts. Studies show that religious leaders use discourse to construct identities, distinguishing between the "faithful" and the "other," thereby reinforcing group cohesion and exclusion (Gee, 2018; Jegede, 2024b). The notion of divine authority allows religious figures to wield significant influence over personal and collective decision-making, often positioning their interpretations as absolute truth (Van Leeuwen, 2021). Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) has been instrumental in exposing the underlying power dynamics in religious communication, illustrating how language serves as a means of ideological reproduction (Wodak

& Meyer, 2021). In the context of apostasy discourse, scholars argue that religious institutions employ discursive strategies to delegitimise dissenters, framing them as deviants or threats to communal stability (Zine, 2020). The use of fear appeals, moral absolutism, and prophetic claims further solidifies the authority of religious leaders while discouraging critical engagement with theological interpretations (Chouliaraki & Fairclough, 2019; Jegede & Okere, 2025). In African literature, authors such as Wole Soyinka critique these discursive mechanisms, exposing how religious rhetoric can be manipulated for personal gain and social control. *The Trials of Brother Jero* exemplifies this critique, portraying how religious discourse is used to establish dominance, deceive followers, and sustain power hierarchies. The analysis of such texts through CDA provides valuable insights into the broader implications of ideology and power in religious discourse, demonstrating how language shapes belief systems and societal structures.

Apostasy Discourse in African Literature and Its Socio-Political Implications

Apostasy discourse in African literature is deeply intertwined with themes of religious authority, cultural identity, and socio-political power. Writers often explore the consequences of religious dissent, revealing the ideological and institutional mechanisms used to suppress or control individuals who challenge dominant faith traditions (Adogame, 2021). Many African societies regard religious identity as a fundamental aspect of communal belonging, making apostasy a contentious issue that extends beyond personal belief to societal stability (Karanja, 2020). Literature serves as a platform for interrogating these tensions, revealing how religious leaders, political institutions, and cultural norms collaborate to marginalize those who reject or question established doctrines (Chitando, 2019). In postcolonial African narratives, apostasy is frequently depicted as a site of conflict between traditional religious values and modernity, with characters exploring the precarious space between personal conviction and societal expectation (Gugler, 2021). Authors such as Wole Soyinka, Chinua Achebe, and Ngũgĩ wa Thiong'o use literary discourse to critique religious fundamentalism and its impact on individual freedoms. *The Trials of Brother Jero* exemplifies this critique, showcasing how religious leaders manipulate theological narratives to maintain authority, control dissent, and shape communal ideologies. Through satire and allegory, such texts expose the socio-political power dynamics embedded in religious discourse, offering a lens into how language functions as a tool of domination and resistance (Gikandi, 2019).

The socio-political implications of apostasy discourse in African literature extend beyond religious critique to broader discussions on governance, human rights, and social transformation. Religious institutions in many African countries wield significant influence over political structures, shaping laws, policies, and public discourse on morality and identity (Ellis & ter Haar, 2018). Apostasy, when framed as a betrayal of communal values, often serves as a pretext for exclusion, persecution, or social ostracization, reinforcing power hierarchies within both religious and political spheres (Zine, 2020). Literature reveals these realities by portraying how dissenting voices are silenced through discourse strategies such as moral condemnation, fear appeals, and legal constraints (Van Dijk, 2015). In societies where religious and political elites operate in tandem, apostasy discourse becomes a means of policing ideological conformity, thereby stifling intellectual and spiritual freedom (Simpson & Mayr, 2019). However, African literary texts also present counter-narratives that challenge these oppressive structures, advocating for pluralism, critical thought, and the reformation of religious institutions (Chilton, 2022). Through character development, dialogue, and symbolism, authors create spaces for reimagining religious identity outside rigid institutional control, offering alternative discourses that promote individual agency and social progress. As apostasy discourse continues to shape socio-political debates in contemporary Africa, literature remains a crucial site for examining the intersections of faith, power, and ideological resistance. Through critical engagement with these themes, African literature not only reflects historical and contemporary struggles but also contributes to the ongoing discourse on religious freedom and social justice.

Theoretical Framework (Van Dijk's CDA Model)

Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA) is a multidisciplinary approach that examines the relationship between language, power, and ideology in discourse. It investigates how discourse constructs and reinforces social structures, often exposing the hidden mechanisms through which dominance and control are maintained (Fairclough, 2015). CDA operates on the premise that language is not neutral but is shaped by and contributes to societal power dynamics (Wodak & Meyer, 2021). Among the prominent scholars in CDA, Teun A. Van Dijk's approach emphasizes the cognitive and social dimensions of discourse, focusing on how ideological structures shape communication and influence public perception (Van Dijk, 2008). His model considers discourse as a means of exercising power, where dominant groups use language to sustain their authority while marginalized groups may challenge these structures through

counter-discourses (Van Dijk, 2013). This framework is particularly relevant to analyzing religious discourse, as it reveals how religious leaders use language to construct ideological narratives that reinforce their influence over followers.

Van Dijk's CDA framework is particularly useful for examining literary texts because literature often reflects and critiques societal power structures. His approach allows for an in-depth analysis of how ideological representations in literary discourse shape readers' perceptions of authority and social norms (Van Dijk, 2015). In *The Trials of Brother Jero*, Soyinka portrays a self-proclaimed prophet who manipulates religious discourse to maintain power and control over his followers. Applying Van Dijk's framework to the play helps uncover the underlying ideological structures that shape Brother Jero's discourse, revealing how language is strategically employed to sustain dominance and deceive others. His model provides a systematic method for identifying discursive strategies such as persuasion, manipulation, and justification, which are central to Brother Jero's characterization. The justification for choosing Van Dijk's approach lies in its ability to link textual analysis with broader social and cognitive processes, making it a suitable tool for dissecting the interplay between ideology, power, and apostasy discourse in the play. This study, therefore, employs Van Dijk's CDA model to explore the mechanisms through which language constructs religious authority and reinforces ideological dominance in *The Trials of Brother Jero*, contributing to a good understanding of the socio-political dimensions of religious discourse.

Methodology

The study adopted a qualitative research design, which was appropriate for interrogating ideology, power, and apostasy in Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero*, since the concern was with the interpretation of language, meaning, and discourse rather than statistical measurement. The data for the study consisted of the primary text of the play, with purposive sampling used to extract passages that reflected key themes such as ideology, power, and the language of apostasy; apostasy, power, and gendered resistance; the discourse of power, apostasy, and the mask of holiness; the language of violence, irony, and disillusionment; and apostasy, ideology, and the corruption of power. The selection criteria focused on dialogues and dramatic scenes where Jeroboam's manipulation of faith, ideological positioning, and discourse strategies were most prominent. Data collection involved close reading of the text with emphasis on linguistic forms, discourse markers, satirical devices, and symbolic representations. Thematic analysis was then applied to identify, code, and categorise recurring patterns that revealed how discourse constructed apostasy,

masked power, and reinforced or resisted domination. This design ensured credibility, trustworthiness, validity, and reliability by employing a systematic interpretive process supported with textual evidence. Although limited by its focus on a single play, the methodology allowed for in-depth engagement with the text, thereby enhancing rigour and transparency. The approach was significant and novel in combining Critical Discourse Analysis to examine apostasy and power in African drama, a perspective underexplored in existing literature.

Findings

The findings of this study present the outcome of a critical discourse analysis of Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero*, focusing on how ideology, power, and apostasy are interwoven in the character of Jeroboam and the broader satirical vision of the play. The analysis examines how Soyinka deploys linguistic strategies, satirical devices, and discourse features to expose religious hypocrisy and manipulation. The findings reveal that Jero's discourse is not only a vehicle of domination and deceit but also a reflection of deeper tensions between spirituality and materialism. The findings are organised under five thematic strands: Ideology, Power, and the Language of Apostasy; Apostasy, Power, and Gendered Resistance; The Discourse of Power, Apostasy, and the Mask of Holiness; The Language of Violence, Irony, and Disillusionment; and Apostasy, Ideology, and the Corruption of Power. These categories provide insights into how Soyinka critiques the interplay of faith and power, unveiling the mechanisms through which apostasy becomes both a personal strategy and a societal danger.

A. Ideology, Power, and the Language of Apostasy

In the opening scene of Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero*, the playwright employs irony, satire, and exaggeration to unmask the ideological underpinnings of religious imposture. Brother Jero's self-introduction, given directly to the audience in the darkened theatre with a spotlight on him, is not merely dramatic flair: it constitutes a performative act that foregrounds the manipulation of discourse as a form of power. Through Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA), one perceives that Jero's words and self-description are not neutral; they are ideological constructions that distort sacred discourse into a secularised economy of gain. His so-called prophetic calling becomes conflated with "trade," a term loaded with commercial and transactional connotations. This linguistic slippage exposes the commodification of spirituality, revealing a

fragmentation, rivalry, and deceit. Soyinka's choice of oxymoronic names for churches, such as "Heavenly Cowboys" (p.10), reveals how language ridicules the absurdity of misaligned spirituality. CDA interprets these names as semiotic markers of ideological dissonance—terms that should invoke holiness are linguistically paired with images of lawlessness. The effect is the exposure of apostasy as cultural spectacle, where the sacred becomes farce through linguistic contradiction.

Furthermore, Soyinka's emphasis on "territorial warfare" (p.10) among prophets shows religion as militarised discourse. The use of martial terminology transforms spiritual leadership into political combat, where land and converts are spoils of war. Jero's verbal contest with the Old Prophet illustrates the intergenerational transmission of corruption: discursive habits of deceit and rivalry are passed from master to apprentice, ensuring continuity of apostasy. The satiric construction of Chume as the "apprentice of God" (p.10.) suggests that the future is not renewal but degeneration, a cultural commentary on how ideology perpetuates itself through discursive reproduction.

Soyinka presents Jero not merely as an individual hypocrite but as the embodiment of an ideological system where language itself is weaponised to legitimise deceit. The constant play on ambiguity, irony, and pun—"ways" as prophetic "tricks," prophecy as "trade"—illustrates how discourse becomes a tool of power. Critical Discourse Analysis reveals that apostasy here is not simply theological deviation but the cultural effect of language stripped of sacred truth and harnessed to self-interest. Soyinka's satire is effective because it forces the audience to confront the complicity of society in tolerating such language, and in doing so, exposes how power, ideology, and discourse together engender spiritual corruption.

B. Apostasy, Power and Gendered Resistance

Scene Two shifts the narrative away from Brother Jero's immediate presence, yet the false prophet's influence lingers as the hidden cause of domestic unrest between Chume and his wife, Amope. Soyinka deliberately masks Jero's role at the outset, creating suspense while foregrounding the corrosive effects of his fraudulent practices. What appears at first to be a comic marital squabble soon reveals the far-reaching consequences of Jero's ideology: the distortion of faith into a system of debt, deception, and exploitation that destabilises both private life and the social order. Through Critical Discourse Analysis, this scene may be read as a dramatization of how the power of religious imposture infiltrates domestic and economic relationships, producing a form of cultural apostasy where spiritual leadership becomes synonymous with material dishonesty.

The confrontation between Chume and Amope initially functions as comic relief, with exaggerated images such as the diminutive Chume pedalling a bicycle overloaded with his wife and her belongings (p.12). Yet beneath the humour lies a discourse of humiliation and powerlessness. Chume's social position as "Chief Messenger" is repeatedly belittled by Amope, who uses language to puncture his masculinity and status. Her invective—contrasting his meagre life with the success of his schoolmates who have become ministers (p.16)—exposes how Soyinka uses dialogue as a vehicle of social critique. Through CDA, one sees how Amope's words reflect broader discourses of postcolonial frustration: ordinary men are trapped in cycles of servitude while those who manipulate power, including religious charlatans like Jero, enrich themselves. Thus, Chume is doubly victimised—at home through verbal emasculation and in public life through his gullibility as Jero's disciple.

The irony deepens when Chume unwittingly delivers his wife to the house of her debtor, not realising that the culprit is his own spiritual master (p.14). Dramatic irony here is not mere theatrical device but a critical exposure of the ideological blindness engendered by Jero's discourse. Through his carefully crafted image of holiness, Jero has persuaded his followers, particularly Chume, to suspend rational suspicion. Chume embodies the credulous believer, whose loyalty to his master blinds him to the prophet's duplicity. Soyinka thus shows how religious impostors weaponise discourse to sustain power: they create illusions of sanctity so convincing that even evidence of their corruption is hidden in plain sight.

The confrontations in Scene Two—between Amope and Chume(p.10), Amope and the trader(p.10), and Amope and Jero(p.11)—illustrate how language becomes a battleground of power. Amope's speech, marked by invective, sharp sarcasm, and persistent nagging, reflects both the comic excess of quarrels and a deeper resistance to male and religious authority. Her insults, ranging from calling her husband a "Chief Messenger" (p.12) with scorn to labelling the fish-seller a "cross-eyed wretch" (p.17), expose a discourse of defiance. In a cultural context where women were often silenced or relegated to submissive roles, Amope's refusal to be silenced positions her as a disruptive voice against patriarchal and religious oppression. CDA reveals the significance of this linguistic agency: Amope challenges Jero's sanctimonious rhetoric, exposing him not through theological argument but through the blunt discourse of debt and accountability.

The dialogue between Amope and Jero is particularly telling. When she addresses him as "bearded debtor" (p.17) rather than "prophet," she strips him of his religious authority through linguistic re-labelling. This act of renaming is

a profound reversal of power: the spiritual leader, accustomed to controlling discourse, is reduced to a common cheat in the eyes of an ordinary woman. Jero's attempt to cloak his debt in pious language—"Beware of pride, sister...I hope you have not come to stand in the way of Christ and his work"—is undercut by Amope's blunt retort: "If Christ does not stand in the way of me and my work" (p.16). The clash here illustrates the ideological struggle between religious deception and economic justice. Amope's refusal to be intimidated demonstrates how everyday language can unmask the hollowness of sanctimonious discourse.

Soyinka exaggerates the scene to heighten both its comic and critical effect. Jero's final escape through a window, accompanied by Amope's shouts of "You bearded rogue," "a thief of a prophet," and "You call yourself a man of God" (p.16), dramatizes the prophet's complete disgrace. The audience, already aware of Jero's hypocrisy from Scene One, now witnesses his symbolic unmasking through public ridicule. From a CDA perspective, this moment marks the collapse of Jero's ideological façade in the private sphere, even though he continues to manipulate his congregation in public. The irony is sharp: Jero, who claims spiritual superiority, is reduced to running from a woman whose only weapon is language. Yet his refusal to repent or relinquish power reinforces Soyinka's central theme: apostasy is not an accident of weakness but a deliberate ideological project sustained by manipulation and shamelessness. Scene Two also contributes to Soyinka's larger critique of the church as an institution complicit in social decay. In making Jero's dishonesty the root of conflict in a believer's household, Soyinka suggests that apostasy does not remain confined to the pulpit; it contaminates family life, marriage, and community. Chume's misplaced loyalty to Jero against his own wife illustrates how spiritual deception disempowers men and erodes domestic harmony. The comic tone may provoke laughter, but beneath the laughter lies a disturbing commentary: when prophets become traders and manipulators, faith ceases to be a source of moral guidance and becomes instead a catalyst for division and strife.

Through this scene, Soyinka not only satirises false prophets but also challenges cultural assumptions about gender and power. Amope, though abrasive and quarrelsome, emerges as a figure of resistance—an African woman who refuses to be silenced by either her husband or the prophet. Her industry, persistence, and refusal to be intimidated offer a counter-narrative to the gullibility of Chume and the deceit of Jero. In this way, Scene Two dramatises the struggle over discourse itself: who has the right to name, accuse, and expose? Soyinka

suggests that the survival of truth in a corrupt society may depend on voices like Amope's, voices willing to challenge hypocrisy even at the cost of ridicule. Thus, Scene Two functions not merely as comic interlude but as an ideological battleground where power, gender, and religious imposture intersect. Through irony, invective, and exaggeration, Soyinka reveals how Jero's ideology extends beyond the pulpit into the intimate fabric of domestic life, producing apostasy not only in faith but also in the ethical relations between men and women. In exposing Jero's hypocrisy through Amope's fearless speech, Soyinka confronts his audience with the uncomfortable truth that apostasy thrives not only through the lies of leaders but also through the silence of those unwilling to question them.

C. The Discourse of Power, Apostasy and the Mask of Holiness

Scene Three intensifies Soyinka's satirical exposure of Brother Jero by foregrounding the contrast between appearance and reality, a tension that encapsulates his ideological manipulation and moral apostasy. Jero's stage entrance in flowing white robes, a velvet cape, and armed with a rod of supposed divine authority (p.9) invokes the visual discourse of purity, sanctity, and prophetic legitimacy. Yet, Soyinka destabilises these symbols, inverting the meaning of "whiteness" into "blackened white." The imagery collapses into oxymoron—purity turned corruption, holiness turned hypocrisy. This linguistic reversal illustrates how Jero's ideology operates: he colonises the sacred symbols of religion but empties them of meaning, leaving a parody of sanctity. The cultural force of the colour "white" within African and Christian cosmologies—denoting purity, moral authority, and divine election—is here subverted, forcing the audience to confront the violence of Jero's misuse of these signifiers.

Jero's soliloquy on page 9 exposes not only his self-deception but also his calculated use of discourse as power. He constructs himself against "charlatans" and "scum" of the prophetic profession, deploying a rhetoric of exclusion to elevate his own supposed uniqueness. Yet, in declaring himself "Velvet-hearted Jeroboam" and "Immaculate Jero" (p.9) he inadvertently unmask his own corruption. The poetic symmetry of "Immaculate Jero" and "Articulate Hero" demonstrates Soyinka's parody of self-aggrandising religious rhetoric: the rhyme and rhythm create harmony in sound but discord in meaning. This linguistic play suggests how religious leaders manipulate language to aestheticise lies, transforming deceit into something palatable. Critical Discourse Analysis here reveals Jero's titles as linguistic tools of power:

designed to captivate the imagination of followers, while concealing the emptiness of his spiritual claims.

The irony is sharpened when we recall that the very velvet cape Jero parades as his badge of holiness was bought on credit from Amope, whose unpaid debt remains unresolved (p.15). His attempt to elevate himself through the same garment renders him doubly unholy: it is not only tainted spiritually but also socially, as it is a stolen symbol of status. Soyinka deliberately exposes the intersection of materialism and spirituality in Jero's apostasy—religion reduced to commerce, holiness commodified as “colour” to market one's prophetic “business.”

Soyinka also unpacks the relational dynamics of power between Jero and Chume. Jero refers to Chume as his “dependable adherent” (p.20), yet the word “dependable” loses its positive connotation and is re-inscribed as a marker of gullibility and subjugation. Chume's earnest complaints about his wife's nagging are cynically manipulated: Jero withholds permission for domestic violence, not out of moral conviction but out of strategic interest. Keeping Chume perpetually dissatisfied ensures his continual dependence on the prophet's authority. This cynical exploitation echoes Althusser's notion of ideological interpellation: Chume is hailed as a subject not of God's truth but of Jero's manipulative discourse, conditioned to derive meaning from dissatisfaction rather than fulfilment.

The irony intensifies when Jero learns that Amope—his creditor—is Chume's wife (p.13). His immediate reversal from forbidding violence to endorsing wife-beating exposes his ideology as wholly opportunistic. Here apostasy is stark: the prophet who should embody the ethic of peace instead sanctions violence to protect his reputation. His invocation of Christian imagery—referring to Amope as Chume's “cross to bear” (p.22)—is grotesquely inverted when he later commands her punishment. Soyinka demonstrates how the sacred language of discipleship can be hijacked to justify cruelty, revealing the ease with which apostate leaders weaponise scripture for personal ends.

Another crucial dimension of Jero's apostasy lies in his prayer practices. His invective-laden prayer for Chume is filled with terms such as “Apostate, Traitor, Sinner, Protector of Baal” (p.23). These terms, although hurled at Chume, describe Jero himself more accurately. This self-revealing projection shows how discourse masks the speaker's corruption while silencing the victim. Critical Discourse Analysis exposes here how religious abuse operates: power is maintained by linguistic violence, where labels delegitimise dissent and create dependency.

Soyinka further critiques the worshippers' complicity. Their prayers, filled with vain repetitions—"Clerk today? Chief Clerk tomorrow. Bicycle today? Car tomorrow" (p.24)—mirror the consumerist ideology of the prophet. Religion becomes a transactional discourse of desire, where the sacred is reduced to material aspiration. The comic spectacle of congregants chorusing "Amen" to Chume's absurd prayers (p.23) unmasks a community intoxicated by illusion, demonstrating how ideology thrives not only through the leader's manipulation but also through the followers' collusion. Apostasy thus emerges not merely as individual corruption but as a collective cultural phenomenon, where misplaced faith sustains fraudulent leadership.

The barren woman's plight reveals the tragedy within the comedy. Her devotion is portrayed as genuine, her vulnerability palpable (p.27). Yet even she becomes ensnared in Jero's economy of false hope. That Jero, himself cynical, can momentarily acknowledge her pain reveals the human cost of apostasy: genuine suffering is instrumentalised for personal gain. Soyinka therefore juxtaposes frivolous desires (cars, promotions) with authentic existential needs (childbearing), showing how apostate prophets indiscriminately exploit both. Scene Three lays bare the full architecture of Jero's apostasy. His ideology rests on three pillars: the commodification of religious symbols, the manipulation of discourse to maintain dependency, and the betrayal of the sacred ethic of care. Soyinka's use of irony, invective, and parody unmasks this ideological edifice, revealing a religion hollowed out by greed and cruelty. The effect is both comic and tragic: laughter at the absurdity of Jero's antics coexists with unease at the recognition of how easily power corrupts faith. In this way, Soyinka compels his audience to confront not only the hypocrisy of one false prophet but also the wider social vulnerability to religious exploitation in postcolonial African contexts.

D. The Language of Violence, Irony and Disillusionment

In Scene Four, Soyinka continues his satirical dismantling of false prophecy by staging the consequences of Jero's manipulative discourse. The setting returns to Jero's home—already marked as the site of debt and deception—and here his negative influence over Chume materialises in action. Having been "permitted" by the prophet to beat his wife (p.33), Chume undergoes a psychological shift from docility to aggression, a transformation rendered comic yet tragic through Soyinka's stage directions and linguistic exaggerations.

Chume's new-found confidence is described in hyperbolic terms—he acts "imperiously," "viciously tying up the mat," and "practically strangling the mat" (pp.34). These exaggerated actions parody his borrowed sense of power,

exposing the fragility of a masculinity that depends not on inner conviction but on external sanction from Jero. The mat, a domestic object, becomes the displaced target of his pent-up frustration, symbolically absorbing the violence meant for Amope. Soyinka's humour here is double-edged: the audience laughs at the absurdity of a man strangling a mat, yet the laughter is uneasy because it points to the disturbing ease with which religious authority can legitimise domestic abuse.

The dialogue between Chume and Amope demonstrates Soyinka's masterful use of invective and irony. Chume's repeated command, "Shut your big mouth!" and his boast that his "period of abstinence is over" (p.33) reveal how Jero's discourse has re-scripted his subjectivity. Chume appropriates the prophet's language of "trial" and "cross" but distorts it into justification for violence. What was once a Christian metaphor for patience and endurance is perverted into a divine license for brutality. Critical Discourse Analysis reveals here how Jero's manipulation of sacred language infiltrates domestic relations, transforming faith into a tool of patriarchal domination.

Amope's resistance provides a counterpoint. She refuses to "budge" until her debt is repaid, daring Chume to "kill" her first (p.34). Her defiance unmasks the irony of her situation: she unknowingly appeals to the same prophet who has authorised her punishment. This dramatic irony not only ridicules her misplaced faith in Jero but also reveals how victims of ideological manipulation can remain blind to its source. Her insults—calling Chume "mad," "foolish," and poor (p.34)—compound the scene's comic hostility, but they also reveal her own complicity in perpetuating cycles of disrespect and broken domestic harmony. The entry of Jero as a hidden observer intensifies the irony. His act of "crossing himself" while watching the quarrel (p.35) signifies his self-delusion, interpreting his cowardly escape from confrontation as divine deliverance. He sees Amope's suffering as providential revenge, further exposing his apostasy. Once again, Soyinka destabilises the signifiers of Christian piety: the gesture of the cross, traditionally sacred, becomes emptied of meaning in Jero's hypocritical performance.

A turning point occurs when Chume discovers Jero's true identity as Amope's debtor. The dramatic build-up—his breathless questioning, "Did I hear you say Prophet Jeroboam?"—culminates in the repeated, fragmented "so... so... so..." (37). This single word, broken into pauses, performs Chume's collapse of faith. The ellipsis captures his shock, his disillusionment, and his belated recognition of betrayal. Here, discourse functions not only as manipulation but also as revelation: the same words that once bound him to Jero now unmask the prophet's deceit.

Soyinka's satire reaches a sharp edge in this moment. Chume, once the gullible disciple, becomes the disillusioned victim who realises he has trusted "the arm of flesh" (cf. Jeremiah 17:5–6). His foolishness is exaggerated for comic effect, but the audience is compelled to sympathise with his plight. Like Sheridan's Sir Peter Teazel, Chume's trust in a hypocritical mentor ends in humiliation. The laughter Soyinka provokes is therefore bittersweet—what the critic Mireku-Gyimah calls "very funny and inexpressibly sad."

Through this scene, Soyinka lays bare the destructive ripple effects of Jero's apostasy: not only is religion corrupted, but social and domestic life is fractured. The irony is that Chume's aggression, supposedly a personal liberation, turns out to be a manipulation serving Jero's selfish escape from debt and public disgrace. Amope's nagging, Chume's gullibility, and Jero's villainy all converge into a tragicomic tableau that satirises the Nigerian socio-religious context.

Scene Four portrays Jero as a "hardened criminal"—a lion prowling for prey (cf. 1 Peter 5:8)—whose corruption of faith engulfs even his most loyal adherents. Soyinka's use of irony, invective, and exaggeration renders the prophet both laughable and dangerous, compelling the audience to confront the absurdity of misplaced trust in charismatic but corrupt leaders. The humour sustains dramatic interest, but beneath the comedy lies a grave social critique: the exposure of how religious manipulation breeds violence, disillusionment, and despair.

E. Apostasy, Ideology and the Corruption of Power

The final scene of *The Trials of Brother Jero* represents the climax of Soyinka's satire, where the prophet's ideology of manipulation fully blossoms into apostasy. At this point, Jero has abandoned even the pretence of spiritual responsibility, replacing it with a calculated pragmatism that treats human beings as disposable instruments. His speech about Chume epitomises this shift: "Oho, I had almost forgotten Brother Chume... Never mind, it was good price to pay for getting rid of my creditor" (p39). The language here is chilling in its casual dismissal. Chume, once his most faithful disciple, is reduced to a mere transaction, sacrificed for Jero's financial convenience. What Critical Discourse Analysis reveals is that Jero's authority is sustained not by moral truth but by a discourse of possession and disposal, in which people are commodified.

The irony of addressing Chume as "Brother" intensifies this apostasy. In Christian discourse, the fraternal term signifies solidarity, compassion and shared faith. Jero's ironic use of the title empties it of meaning, exposing a hollow religiosity where sacred language functions only as a mask for

exploitation. Soyinka invites the audience to recognise how power operates through such linguistic distortions: words associated with love and fraternity become instruments of betrayal. The effect is a double exposure—of Jero as a hypocrite and of religion itself as vulnerable to co-option by opportunists.

This ideological corruption is deepened when Jero pronounces Chume “insane” (p.43). Labelling functions here as a strategy of exclusion and silencing. In designating dissent as madness, Jero exercises discursive power that aligns disturbingly with political authoritarianism. Chume’s anger and resistance, rather than being recognised as legitimate protest, are pathologised. Soyinka thus exposes the way religious and political institutions collaborate in delegitimising opposition, a critique that aligns with postcolonial African contexts where dissenting voices were often branded subversive or irrational.

The introduction of the Member of Parliament marks a further degeneration of Jero’s ideology. Having lost Chume, he turns to a new “victim,” describing the politician with the contemptuous metaphor “poor fish” (p.42). The image collapses the distance between a supposedly powerful legislator and a hapless prey already ensnared in the prophet’s net. The irony lies in the inversion of expected hierarchies: the honourable politician, a representative of the people, is demeaned by the very charlatan he seeks out for advancement. This reversal not only ridicules the politician’s vanity but also indicts a culture of political opportunism that renders leaders susceptible to manipulation.

Soyinka sharpens his critique through the darkly comic promise of the “Minister for War” portfolio (p.40). The hyperbolic claim that this would be “the most powerful position in the land” (p.40) reveals the grotesque logic of both prophet and politician: power is defined not by service or peace but by violence. The linguistic ambiguity of “for war”—suggesting not stewardship but advocacy—intensifies the irony, indicting African leaders who, in the guise of diplomacy, perpetuate conflict for personal enrichment. The satire here is not merely national but continental, exposing how both religious and political discourses collude in sustaining cycles of violence and exploitation.

Chume’s return, disillusioned and armed with a cutlass, provides a tragic counterpoint to the politician’s gullibility. His anguished repetition of “Why? Why? Why? Why?” (p.41) aligns beyond his personal betrayal. The questioning dramatizes a collective experience of deception, inviting the audience to reflect on their own susceptibility to manipulation. The linguistic fragmentation mirrors a collapse of meaning, a moment where language itself falters in the face of betrayal. Yet Soyinka frames this breakdown ironically, making the audience laugh even as they identify with Chume’s despair. The effect is satirical

estrangement: through laughter, spectators are forced to confront uncomfortable truths about their complicity in enabling false prophets. The conclusion of the play, where Jero arranges to have Chume confined to a lunatic asylum (p.44), epitomises apostasy as the logical end of his ideology. Here, spiritual authority merges with political coercion, and religious discourse becomes indistinguishable from authoritarian violence. Jero’s triumph—“And so the day is saved” (44)—is bitterly ironic, transforming the language of salvation into a celebration of oppression. In Critical Discourse terms, this represents the total inversion of religious language: salvation is equated with silencing dissent, brotherhood with exploitation, prophecy with fraud. Through Scene Five, Soyinka’s satire acquires its sharpest political edge. Apostasy is not presented as a mere personal failing but as the cultural consequence of a society where power, both religious and political, thrives on gullibility, fear and ambition. The collusion between prophet and politician symbolises the nexus of corruption in postcolonial Africa, where spiritual fraudulence and political opportunism reinforce each other. Thus, the play closes with a warning: Jero is not an isolated figure but a type, a recurring “riff-raff” whose apostasy mirrors systemic decay. Soyinka’s strategy—irony, exaggeration, invective—does more than ridicule; it compels recognition of the ideological mechanisms that allow such figures to flourish. The laughter provoked is therefore uneasy, forcing the audience to ask why societies repeatedly surrender themselves to manipulation and what might break the cycle of complicity.

Discussion of Findings

This study set out to examine Jeroboam’s ideology and the exercise of power in Wole Soyinka’s *The Trials of Brother Jero* through the lens of Critical Discourse Analysis (CDA). The findings reveal that ideology in the play is sustained through language that manipulates, conceals, and legitimises authority. Jeroboam’s discourse exemplifies what Fairclough terms “hegemonic discourse,” where individuals willingly submit to power because it is couched in persuasive rhetoric. Such manipulation demonstrates how apostasy in the play is constructed not as theological deviation but as discursive abuse of authority for self-serving ends. The results confirm earlier scholarship which recognises language as central to Soyinka’s satirical vision (Mireku-Gyimah, 2013; Osoba, 2014). In Jeroboam’s discourse, irony, presupposition, and deliberate misrepresentation become pragmatic strategies to lure followers into compliance, revealing the role of language in shaping ideology. The analysis therefore positions Soyinka’s satire as a critique of institutionalised religion,

which fails not merely in doctrine but in its surrender to manipulative rhetoric that veils hypocrisy. The study thus addresses the first research question, showing that apostasy is linguistically and pragmatically constructed, serving as an ideological device that exposes the perversion of spiritual leadership.

The results also show that Soyinka's depiction of apostasy is linked to power relations that extend into questions of resistance and compliance. Jeroboam's manipulation of discourse constructs a hierarchy where male authority is centralised, and the congregation—especially women—become subjects of exploitation. The laity's vulnerability reveals not only the strength of manipulative rhetoric but also the complicity of followers in sustaining apostate leadership. This supports Mireku-Gyimah's (2013) argument that Soyinka's satire is socially anchored, targeting both leaders and the wider society that tolerates corruption. In relation to gender, Jero's authority is sustained through rhetorical seduction that masks predatory tendencies, illustrating the intersection of power, discourse, and gendered subjugation. Mackwan's (2018) observation that conflict in the play emerges from tension between authentic spirituality and manipulative religiosity aligns with these findings, as resistance from certain characters reveals the cracks in Jero's constructed authority. Apostasy in this sense is not only a matter of theological compromise but also of gendered exploitation, sustained through discourse that presents manipulation as prophetic calling. The results indicate that apostasy functions as a cultural and a spiritual deviation embedded in power structures that privilege domination and silence resistance.

One of the central findings of the study is the way Soyinka unmasks apostasy through the satirical exposure of religious discourse. Jero's prophetic persona is sustained through what Ekpe, Anita, and Ako (2013) term "language engineering," a process in which words are weaponised to create authority while masking moral emptiness. This discursive mask of holiness enables Jero to legitimise his personal ambitions under the guise of spiritual piety. The study reveals that apostasy is enacted through this mask, where sanctity is performed through rhetoric rather than lived integrity. In relation to earlier scholarship, these findings confirm Davoodifar and Pourya Asl's (2015) Foucauldian reading of the play, which reveals the intricate connection between power and discourse. The results extend this argument by showing that Jero's mask of holiness is not simply theatrical but deeply ideological, as it exploits contextual presuppositions to perpetuate obedience. The construction of apostasy through discourse thus demonstrates that the exercise of power is not overt coercion but subtle manipulation cloaked in religious rhetoric. The findings respond directly to the study's second research question, demonstrating that Jero's

manipulation illustrates religious hypocrisy that thrives in the absence of critical resistance.

The findings also reveal that Soyinka's satire employs irony and ridicule as tools to unmask apostasy and reveal the violence embedded in religious discourse. Jero's authority depends on a form of linguistic violence, where truth is obscured, and followers are coerced into compliance through deceptive strategies. This aligns with Abisola's (2011) and Sanka and Cecilia's (2013) observations that Soyinka deploys comedy and satire as corrective instruments against societal ills. While humour in the play generates laughter, it simultaneously exposes the disillusionment of followers who realise the futility of their obedience. The irony in Jero's language mirrors Ajiboye's (2020) claim about pragmatic roles sustaining humour, but this study extends the point by demonstrating how humour also constructs ideological dominance and resistance. The disillusionment of characters reflects the play's broader critique of religious leadership, showing how the weaponisation of language leads to spiritual disorientation. Apostasy in this framework is exposed through the irony of a prophet who claims divine calling but embodies corruption, thereby positioning satire as both mirror and weapon against discursive abuse.

The final set of findings demonstrates that Soyinka's portrayal of Jero situates apostasy within the broader dynamics of ideology and the corruption of power. Apostasy is shown as a discursive phenomenon that undermines communal trust and ethical spirituality, transforming religion into an arena of power struggle. The study confirms that apostasy should not be narrowly conceived as doctrinal error but as ideological corruption that distorts discourse for personal gain. This reinforces Mackwan's (2018) view of conflict between authentic spirituality and manipulative religiosity, while advancing the discussion through CDA by providing insight into how language enacts power. Importantly, the data reveal that the corruption of power in the play mirrors contemporary realities in which religious rhetoric is exploited for political or personal ends. The findings therefore respond to the third research question, showing that Soyinka's satire critiques apostasy not only as a spiritual failure but as a social and ideological crisis. Apostasy becomes a communal rather than individual phenomenon, implicating both leaders and followers in the corruption of spiritual and moral values.

Conclusion

The study concludes that Wole Soyinka's *The Trials of Brother Jero* reveals the intersection of ideology, power, and the language of apostasy, showing how discourse becomes a strategic tool for sustaining religious deception and

legitimising personal ambition. The findings establish that apostasy is enacted not only through the manipulation of faith but also through the silencing of dissent and the marginalisation of gendered voices, foregrounding apostasy, power, and gendered resistance in the struggle between domination and subversion. Soyinka further unmasks the contradictions of false religiosity through the discourse of power, apostasy, and the mask of holiness, where the prophet cloaks materialistic ambitions in pretence of spiritual authority. The study also demonstrates how Soyinka relies on the language of violence, irony, and disillusionment to satirise religious hypocrisy, exposing the emotional and social consequences of misplaced trust in deceptive leaders. The results affirm that apostasy, ideology, and the corruption of power are central to Soyinka's critique, providing insights into how language is weaponised to entrench control, distort faith, and perpetuate exploitation. Through the application of Critical Discourse Analysis, this study not only fills a gap in scholarship by linking apostasy directly to discourse strategies of power but also advances theoretical and practical contributions. Theoretically, it strengthens the relevance of discourse pragmatics in African drama; practically, it offers a cautionary framework for contemporary audiences to interrogate the rhetoric of religious and political leaders. Thus, the study enriches academic discourse while revealing the socio-religious dangers of apostasy in the African context.

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